

Surgical Case

Mandible Reconstruction Using Free Fibula Flap

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Since 1983, the free fibula flap gains the domains each after the other. The side effects of its harvest in site donor are well tolerated. Whereas the benefits of its implantation in site recipient are of great value.

Previously, in three reported cases, I presented some examples of its valuable contributions in plastic surgery; the maxilla, the radius bone, and the ulna bone reconstruction.

Herein, I will present another reported case concerning the mandible reconstruction using the same versatile flap. The patient is a 31-year-old female, was a victim of a gun shout. She lost the total nose, the middle portion of the maxilla, and the anterior arc of the mandible. The total left horizontal ramus, the total chin bone, and most of the right horizontal ramus of the mandible were absent; Figures (1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7).

Figure (1)
Pre- Operative X- Ray

Panoramic dental X-ray reveals the bone defects in the nose, the maxilla, and the mandible. In the mandible, the total left horizontal ramus, chin bone, and most of the right horizontal ramus, all are absent.

Figure (2)
Pre- Operation Face Photo

Figure (3)
Pre- Operation Profile

Figure (4)

Per- Operative View, Vascularized Fibula Flap

Fibula flap is still in place connected to its pedicle

Figure (5- a)

Figure (5- b)

Figure (5)

Per- Operative Views, Vascularized Fibula Flap

Figure (5- a): *The free fibula flap, of 16cm long, is harvested with its vascular pedicle.*

Figure (5 -b): *The fibula is reformed as a horse-shoe like in order to replace the mandible bone lost. The forceps indicates to the vascular pedicle.*

Figure (6- a)

Figure (6- b)

Figure (6)

Per- Operative Views, Vascularized Fibula Flap

Figure (6- a): The fibula flap is reformed as a horse-shoe like in order to replace the bone defect in mandible.

Figure (6- b): The reformed free fibula flap in its final place. The vascular pedicle of the flap is anastomosed to the right facial pedicle.

Figure (7- a): Photo from Below

Figure (7- b): Profile Photo

Figure (7)

Per- Operative Views

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- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(1\), the Pathophysiology of Hyperactivity*](#)
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- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(3\), the Pathophysiology of Extended Hyperreflex*](#)
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- [DOI *The Nerve Transmission through Neural Fiber, Personal View vs. International View*](#)
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- - [*The Three Phases of Nerve transmission*](#)

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- - *Nodes of Ranvier, Third Function*
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- - *The Neural Regeneration*
- - *The Wallerian Degeneration Attacks Motor Axons, While Avoids Sensory Axons*

- DOI *The Sensory Receptors*

- - *Nerve Conduction Study, Wrong Hypothesis is the Origin of the Misinterpretation (Innovated)*

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